

Full Length Research Paper

Financial cost implication of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) resurgence in Oyo State: the 2015 episode

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Highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) is a very destructive disease of poultry as it causes high death rate within a flock and affects the livelihood of farmers. Oyo state experienced previous outbreaks of avian influenza (A.I.) before the bio-containment in 2006/2007. Resurgence of avian influenza was confirmed by the Oyo State avian influenza desk officer as at February 2015. This study analyzed previous methods of assessing losses due to avian influenza, and used a revised economic model to calculate costs associated with the avian influenza resurgence in Oyo State. The evaluation used epidemiological data, production figures and other input parameters to determine the final costs. The infection caused a loss of 200,272,800 Naira (\$910,330.91) in Oyo State. This study urges government to develop an avian

influenza emergency preparedness system coupled with a rapid response initiative, which must be tested regularly to forestall a future resurgence bearing in mind the huge economic losses associated with the disease. The cost implication of a disease outbreak is an important tool for proper decision making, especially in the case of highly pathogenic avian influenza. The time lag between disease outbreak and intervention can worsen the economic effects of the disease thereby causing farmers to lose their livelihood. Disease control decision making processes now involves a multidisciplinary approach, thus making outcomes of decisions highly effective.

Keywords: Avian influenza, Oyo State, poultry, resurgence, financial impact

INTRODUCTION

Highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) is a very destructive disease of poultry as it causes high death rate within a flock and affects the livelihood of farmers (Wakawa *et al.*, 2008). The 2004 agricultural gross domestic product (GDP) in 2004 from the poultry sector

was approximately 4.45%, thus confirming that it is a major source of income in Nigeria (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2004). Evaluating the cost implication of the aftermath of livestock diseases is very difficult (Holtz-Eakin, 2005). Highly pathogenic avian influenza outbreaks

occurred on farms in Nigeria in 2006 and more than 200000 chickens died. Farms with survivors were depopulated (Gardner *et al.*, 2007). During a field survey necessitating a visit to the avian influenza desk officer for Oyo state (A Government official), his notes confirmed the resurgence of avian influenza in Oyo state as at February, 2015.

The official confirmation of HPAI in Nigeria by government and nongovernmental agencies has in times past led to apprehension by farmers and panic by consumers, hence resulting in consumers avoiding poultry and poultry products (UNDP, 2006). It is possible for chicken eggs and chicken sales to decline by 80.5% within 2 weeks and such a situation can linger on for up to 4 months (UNDP, 2006). In some previous studies farm workers of infected farms lost their jobs while a great percent of farm workers on unaffected farms also lost their jobs (UNDP, 2006). Socio-economic evaluation model reviews of previous experiences showed that the cost implication of a disease is the sum of direct, indirect, intangible and costs of intervention (Holtz-Eakin, 2005). Hence, there is a need to determine the economic consequences of avian influenza outbreak and assess the financial cost implication of highly pathogenic avian influenza towards designing contingency plans to prevent resurgence in Oyo State.

METHODOLOGY

Study approach

An appraisal of the economic impacts of the re-emergence of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) outbreaks and government intervention (including compensation) in Oyo State (Nigeria) was done.

Study area

Oyo State, (8.000°N 4.000°E) cover approximately an area of 28,454 square kilometers and is ranked 14th by size. Agriculture is the main occupation of the people of Oyo State. Ibadan is located in South-western Nigeria. It is the capital of Oyo state.

Its population is estimated to be about 3,800,000 according to 2006 estimates. A field survey necessitating a visit to the avian influenza desk officer for Oyo state (A Government official), shared his notes with us and hence, reports getting to the state through him after making a diagnosis from samples taken from suspected farms, confirmed the resurgence of avian influenza in Oyo state as at February, 2015. The choice of Ibadan in Oyo state in the study was because samples brought from that region tested positive to highly pathogenic avian influenza (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Map showing places affected with highly pathogenic avian influenza in Oyo State.

Data management and analysis

The study focused on four farms (with 3,500; 12,000; 700; and 2,000 commercial layer chickens) that were confirmed having avian influenza from February to July, 2015 in Ibadan, Oyo State. A number of assumptions were made because all the farms affected were commercial laying farms:

- (i) Each laying bird laying at 80% production = 284 eggs per laying year.
- (ii) Cost of medication, farm attendant, security, Veterinary Doctor, and miscellaneous expenses was = 1,284 naira.
- (iii) Cost of laying birds as at the time of depopulation = 1,200 naira.
- (iv) Cost of each egg = 30 naira.

Economics of the outbreak was appraised using mathematical models:

$$(C_i = PS \{ \upsilon + \beta + \delta + \gamma \})$$

$$\text{Or } C_i = PS\upsilon + PS\beta + PS\delta + PS\gamma$$

Where

C_i = cost implications
 P = Population of poultry

S = Susceptibility rate of population

υ = direct losses: losses from mortalities (cost due to mortality of poultry and values of chicks lost from breeders)

β = indirect losses: egg and meat loss (value of direct loss of eggs due to yield reduction, cost of rejection of poultry meat and eggs, and cost associated with glut)

δ = Intangible losses: opportunity cost (cost of rearing replacement stock to production or sale point, cost of feeding to point of production, cost of retaining facilities and staff during downtime and rearing stage, and cost of destroying remaining population of animals)

γ = Miscellaneous costs (cost of intense campaign to win back consumer confidence, cost of control and administrative/governmental policies, and external inputs) (Fasina *et al.*, 2008).

Calculating for υ (direct costs)

PS υ 1 = Actual determined direct value based on the outbreak situation (January to August, 2015)

PS υ 2 = Estimated direct value based on mild scenario of HPNAI Outbreak (10% losses in commercial poultry population).

PS υ 3 = Estimated direct value based on severe scenario of HPNAI outbreak (70% losses in commercial poultry population).

PS υ = Market value of birds + value of chicks lost (Fasina *et al.*, 2008).

Calculating for β (indirect costs)

PS β = Cost (glut)

Costs associated with glut: reduction in price observed \times (total annual national production [trays per annum] – trays lost to mortality in HPNAI) (Fasina *et al.*, 2008).

Calculating for δ (intangible costs)

Since intangible costs are costs of rearing replacement stock, Facilities retention, staff retention, downtime cost and destruction/disposal of remaining of affected flocks, therefore:

PS δ = Replacement cost + downtime cost + destruction/disposal cost

Replacement cost = (99.985% cost for raising pullets to POL* + 0.015 % cost for layer breeders pullets to POL) \times total number lost

* POL: Point of lay bird

Downtime cost for facilities = Facility cost per bird per annum \times downtime period per annum \times number of birds.

(N100 per bird per annum \dagger \times 3/12 months \times number of birds \dagger \$778.21 per 1 000 birds per annum for retaining poultry pen) (Field investigations and data from poultry producers, 2006) (Fasina *et al.*, 2008).

RESULTS

Use of Mathematical Models in assessing impact of avian influenza on the farms

Fashina *et al.* (2008) made Mathematical models

$$C_i = PS \{ \upsilon + \beta + \delta + \gamma \}$$

$$\text{Or } C_i = PS\upsilon + PS\beta + PS\delta + PS\gamma$$

As shown in materials and methods

Assumptions

Given that each laying bird laying at 80% production = 284 eggs per laying year.

Working with the assumption that cost of medication, farm attendant, security, cost of medical intervention and miscellaneous expenses was = 1,284 naira,

Cost of laying birds as at the time of depopulation = 1,200 naira,

Cost of each egg = 30 naira,

Therefore applying the formula

$$C_i = PS\upsilon + PS\beta + PS\delta + PS\gamma$$

Impact assessment for farm A

Population of birds = 3,500 laying birds

To calculate direct loss (PS υ)

PS υ = Population of birds \times Cost of each bird

$$= 3,500 \times 1,200 \text{ naira}$$

$$= 4,200,000 \text{ naira}$$

Calculating for indirect costs (PS β)

PS β = Cost of eggs that was supposed to have been sold for the laying year would be calculated as = Population of birds \times Total number of eggs expected per \times Cost of each egg

$$= 3500 \times 284 \times 30$$

$$= 29,820,000 \text{ naira}$$

Calculating for intangible costs (PS δ)

PS δ = Cost of medication, farm attendant, security, medical

intervention cost, and miscellaneous expenses was =
 $1,284 \text{ naira} \times \text{Population of laying birds}$
 $= 1,284 \times 3,500$
 $= 4,494,000 \text{ naira}$

Using the mathematical model:

$C_i = PS_{\alpha} + PS_{\beta} + PS_{\delta} + PS_{\gamma}$
 $C_i = 4,200,000 + 29,820,000 + 4,494,000$
 $= 38,514,000 \text{ naira}$
 $= 175,063.64 \text{ Dollars}$

Impact assessment for farm B

Population of birds = 12,000 laying birds
 To calculate direct loss (PS_{α})
 $PS_{\alpha} = \text{Population of birds} \times \text{Cost of each bird}$
 $= 12,000 \times 1,200 \text{ naira}$
 $= 14,400,000 \text{ naira}$

Calculating for indirect costs (PS_{β})

$PS_{\beta} = \text{Cost of eggs that was supposed to have been sold for the laying year would be calculated as} =$
 $\text{Population of birds} \times \text{Total number of eggs expected per} \times \text{Cost of each egg}$
 $= 12,000 \times 284 \times 30$
 $= 102,240,000 \text{ naira}$

Calculating for intangible costs (PS_{δ})

$PS_{\delta} = \text{Cost of medication, farm attendant, security, medical intervention cost, and miscellaneous expenses was} = 1,284 \text{ naira} \times \text{Population of laying birds}$
 $= 1,284 \times 12,000$
 $= 15,408,000 \text{ naira}$

Using the mathematical model:

$C_i = PS_{\alpha} + PS_{\beta} + PS_{\delta} + PS_{\gamma}$
 $C_i = 14,400,000 + 102,240,000 + 15,408,000$
 $= 132,048,000 \text{ naira}$
 $= \$600,218.18$

Impact assessment for farm C

Population of birds = 700 laying birds
 To calculate direct loss (PS_{α})
 $PS_{\alpha} = \text{Population of birds} \times \text{Cost of each bird}$
 $= 700 \times 1,200 \text{ naira}$
 $= 840,000 \text{ naira}$

Calculating for Indirect Costs (PS_{β})

$PS_{\beta} = \text{Cost of eggs that was supposed to have been}$

sold for the laying year would be calculated as =
 $\text{Population of birds} \times \text{Total number of eggs expected per} \times \text{Cost of each egg}$
 $= 700 \times 284 \times 30$
 $= 5,964,000 \text{ naira}$

Calculating for Intangible costs (PS_{δ})

$PS_{\delta} = \text{Cost of medication, farm attendant, security, medical intervention cost, and miscellaneous expenses was} = 1,284 \text{ naira} \times \text{Population of laying birds}$
 $= 1,284 \times 700$
 $= 898,800 \text{ naira}$

Using the mathematical model:

$C_i = PS_{\alpha} + PS_{\beta} + PS_{\delta} + PS_{\gamma}$
 $C_i = 840,000 + 5,964,000 + 898,800$
 $= 7,702,800 \text{ naira}$
 $= 35,012.727 \text{ Dollars}$

Impact Assessment for Farm D

Population of birds = 2,000 laying birds
 To calculate direct loss (PS_{α})
 $PS_{\alpha} = \text{Population of birds} \times \text{Cost of each bird}$
 $= 2,000 \times 1,200 \text{ naira}$
 $= 2,400,000 \text{ naira}$

Calculating for Indirect Costs (PS_{β})

$PS_{\beta} = \text{Cost of eggs that was supposed to have been sold for the laying year would be calculated as} =$
 $\text{Population of birds} \times \text{Total number of eggs expected per} \times \text{Cost of each egg}$
 $= 2,000 \times 284 \times 30$
 $= 17,040,000$

Calculating for Intangible costs (PS_{δ})

$PS_{\delta} = \text{Cost of medication, farm attendant, security, medical intervention cost, and miscellaneous expenses was} = 1,284 \text{ naira} \times \text{Population of laying birds}$
 $= 1,284 \times 2,000$
 $= 2,568,000 \text{ naira}$

Using the mathematical model:

$C_i = PS_{\alpha} + PS_{\beta} + PS_{\delta} + PS_{\gamma}$
 $C_i = 2,400,000 + 17,040,000 + 2,568,000$
 $= 22,008,000 \text{ naira}$
 $= \$100,036.36$

Therefore,

Total impact of the four farms:

$C_i = \text{Impact on farms A, B, C and D}$

= 38,514,000 naira + 132,048,000 naira + 7,702,800 naira + 22,008,000 naira
 = 200,272,800 Naira
 = \$910,330.91

Impact assessment /compensation package

Only two of the farms were compensated about 4 weeks after their farms were being depopulated after their farms were being confirmed to have had Avian Influenza. A 40 year old male owner of Farm A said, "we lost approximately two million naira as a results of birds that died during the outbreak while approximately one and a half million naira was lost due to total depopulation of the remaining birds and as at now we have not been compensated" (That was as at March 2015). A 52 year old owner of Farm B said, Government promised to compensate us, by paying #1,450 (One thousand four hundred and fifty naira only) per bird". I have been compensated with 920 (nine hundred and twenty) naira per bird, although the compensation reached me exactly four weeks after my farm was depopulated". Another farmer who owns Farm D located along Moniya-Iseyin road in Akinyele Local Government Area said, "The avian influenza outbreak caused a great loss to me. My birds started to die suddenly. I lost about 1,300 birds to the disease and a further 724 birds to depopulation. As at the time of this interview, I have not been compensated". However, after periodical visits to these farmers we confirmed that they were compensated 6 months after the outbreak occurred.

DISCUSSION

Poultry farming is a thriving business in Nigeria. Whenever infectious diseases occur, it deals a heavy blow on the economic activities of the poultry farmers. Governments with inactive disease surveillance and emergency preparedness system are ill-prepared in the eventuality of a disease outbreak and hence focus on funding control campaigns, instead of funding the prevention of the outbreak. The cost implication of a disease outbreak is an important tool for proper decision making, especially in the case of Highly Pathogenic avian Influenza. The time lag between disease outbreak and intervention can worsen the economic effects of the disease thereby causing farmers to lose their livelihood. Losing 200,272,800 Naira (\$910,330.91) in only four (4) farms, due to the effects of avian influenza on only egg laying chickens in this study is a huge economic loss by all standards. It is pitiable that there are no documented records to show the true economic losses of farmers in disease outbreaks. The case of highly pathogenic avian influenza is quite typical of such anomaly. The financial effects of avian influenza

resurgence do involve most farmers losing their livelihood as a result of culling of birds by Government officials. Some farmers never recover from the loss and hence are discouraged from re-embarking on poultry production. A delay in the compensation (coming 6 months after the depopulation) would affect the farmers such that they may never be able to recover from the aftermath of the avian influenza outbreak. Compensation with about half of the value that government promised would definitely discourage other farmers further from reporting suspected avian influenza cases to appropriate Government quarters.

Conclusion

The cost implication of a disease outbreak is an important tool for proper decision making, especially in the case of highly pathogenic avian influenza. The time lag between disease outbreak and intervention can worsen the economic effects of the disease thereby causing farmers to lose their livelihood. It is necessary to also incorporate the unrealised worth of a laying bird or unrealised worth of a bird for meat when calculating the true economic loss of farms ravaged by highly pathogenic Avian Influenza. It is also important to factor in losses at the respective feed mills, hatcheries and even the entire poultry value chain when embarking on a broad based economic appraisal of losses from highly pathogenic avian influenza outbreak. Late compensation and under valuing after depopulating farms in an avian influenza outbreak situation, would discourage other farmers from reporting if, or when they notice avian influenza signs in their flock. Disease control decision making processes now involves a multidisciplinary approach, thus making outcomes of decisions highly effective.

Recommendation

Governments should develop an avian influenza emergency preparedness system coupled with a rapid response initiative, which must be tested regularly to forestall a future outbreak of Avian Influenza. Government should also increase disease surveillance activities in high risk areas. They must also ensure that public enlightenment campaigns are put in place to allow the public know about the economic impact of avian influenza. A space-time model can be developed to predict the likely occurrence of a future avian influenza outbreak in order to put in place measures to prevent the predicted outbreak.

Authors` Declaration

We declare that this study is an original research by our research team and we agree to publish it in the journal.

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